

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL AND IT'S EFFECT ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION

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Abstract

Employee performance is an organization's strength, and human resource managers have historically prioritized employee performance. As a consequence, a variety of performance assessment approaches have been developed throughout time to assist in determining an employee's performance. In modern times, the usage of performance assessments has expanded beyond judging an employee's performance to include variables such as motivation. As a result, attempted to explore the efficacy of performance rating methods and their impact on employee motivation. In the realm of performance management, performance evaluation is a frequently debated issue. The main Objectives of the study was to analyze the effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee Motivation and to identify the challenges in appraising employee's performance. The study significantly used primary data. Some sources for secondary data were also browsed in order to deeply understand the phenomenon of performance appraisal as a basis for Job Satisfaction and Motivation to work. The primary data was collected as responses from a judgment sample of 200 respondents working in various IT industries using simple random sampling technique. The rationale for choosing the respondents was a minimum of a two year work experience in the same organization and being subjected to an annual Performance Appraisal. According to the result of the challenges, it is found that the role of the managers or superiors play main role in performance appraisal.

Keywords

Performance Appraisal and Management Appraisal Compensation. Performance Management, Employee Appraisal and Human Resource

1. Introduction

In the realm of performance management, performance evaluation is a frequently debated issue. Today's business climate necessitates performance evaluation systems because organizations must fulfil organizational goals while also traditional cultural in intensely competitive marketplaces through outstanding

employee performance. When it comes to how personnel do their tasks, organization have a say. Research on performance management also shows that a large number of employees want to achieve well in their industries since it is both a component of their own goals and an indication that they are dedicated to the

business.¹ In Performance Appraisal Concept firms continue to employ informal and subjective performance assessment procedures to determine award choices, the study stated that objective performance evaluation practices are becoming more common in recent years (Gardner, 2008; Sheilds, 2007)². Gardner (2008) defined performance assessment as the examination of an individual's work with the primary goal of reaching objective personnel choices. It is also defined as the process of

gathering, assessing, and documenting information pertaining to an employee's relative value to the firm (Armstrong, 2009)³. This occurs as a result of the intentional contact between an organization's supervisors and workers, in which the former evaluate the latter's performance. One of the primary purposes of the study was to identify strengths and weaknesses that will serve as foundation for proposing steps to enhance employee performance.⁴

2. Employee Motivation as a Concept

Wolff and Gunkel (2007)⁵ explored that "the readiness to expend high levels of effort toward organizational objectives, conditioned by the effort's capacity to meet particular individual needs" Chiang and Jan (2008)⁶ stated employee motivation may be

summed up as "the process of an employee being moved to work" Motivation frequently stems from an individual's psychological need to fulfil urges that have gone unfulfilled, according to the author.⁷ Miao et al. (2007)⁸, intrinsic motivation involved an internal state responsible for activating behaviour as well as the

¹ Erdogan, B. (2002). "Antecedents and consequences of justice perceptions in performance appraisals". *Human Resource Management Review*, 12 (4), 555-578

² Gardner, C.E. (2008) ,"Employee evaluation: is it worth the effort?" *DVM*, 18(5), pp. 647- 81

³ Armstrong, M. (2009), "Armstrong's Handbook of Performance Management: An Evidence Based Guide to Delivering High Performance". London: Kogan Page Publishers

⁴ Bretz R.D., Milovich G.T. Kc Read W.(1992). "The current state of performance research and practice: Concerns, directions, and implications". *Journal of Management*, 18: 321-352

⁵ Wolff, B., Gunkel, M., Lusk, E. J., & Li, F. (2007) "Gender-specific effects at work: an empirical study

of four countries", *Gender, Work & Organization*, 14(1), pp.56-79.

⁶ Chiang, C. and Jan, S. (2008) "An expectancy theory model for hotel employee motivation", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27(2), pp.313-322

⁷ Vasset F.,Mamburg. E. and Furunes,T. (2012),"Dyadic Relationships and Exchange in Performance Appraisal", *Vard Norden*, 32,4-9(9)

⁸ Miao, C., Evans, R. and Shaoming Z. (2007) "The role of salesperson motivation in sales control systems — Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation revisited" *Journal of Business Research*, 60(5), pp.417-425.

circumstances that begin change. Internal motivation is described as a type of human resource motivation that covers work done for the sake of work. Intrinsically motivated employees are those who receive benefits in the form of psychological well-being, self-actualization, increasing responsibility, and self-sustenance. While in the field of human resources, extrinsic motivation is described as the value that employees place on external incentives such as promotions and raises in salary (mark). Potential for dismissal or demotion may also be included in the package. (Lee 2007)⁹. While in the field of human resources, extrinsic motivation is described as the value that employees place on external rewards such as raises and promotions in salary (mark). Potential for dismissal or demotion may also be included in the package. (Van Herpen, Van Praag, and Cools, 2005)¹⁰. The idea of agency suggests that incentives supplied by organization as a method of enhancing an individual's intrinsic drive are usually necessary. In this case, the workers' activities and performance are dictated by the rewards or penalties they get for their behavior. Similarly, the expectation theory asserts that rewarding employees based on their performance encourages them to put in more effort and deliver better results.¹¹.

3. Performance Evaluation for Promotional Motivation

As part of the performance assessment process, evaluators examine the employee's performance and offer a

performance number. (Kumar, 2012)¹². To motivate employees, management utilizes the performance number to construct a performance level number (LPN), which serves as a basis for calculating incentives. Managers can use the LPN as a guide for internal promotions when new roles above the entry level become available.. According to Maana (2008)¹³, promoting an employee not only honours their prior achievements, but it also helps inspire confidence in their coworkers that their hard work will be recognized in the future. As a consequence, everyone else in the company feels compelled to raise their game.

4. Enhancing Employee Motivation through Performance Appraisal

The importance of performance evaluation in gauging an employee's output and monitoring the organization's progress toward its targeted goals and objectives cannot be overstated. Human resource departments and corporate policy are now working together to implement performance assessment as a strategic tool. Because it encompasses a wide range of operations, such as assessing employees' talents, improving their performance, and allocating monetary compensation, they are focusing on it. Individual and organizational goals are better aligned with the assistance of performance evaluation. The system encourages, engages, and leads personnel toward the organization's strategic goals.

⁹ Lee, S.-Y. and Whitford, A.B. (2007) "Exit, voice, loyalty, and pay: evidence from the public workforce", *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), pp. 647- 648.

¹⁰ Van Herpen, M., Van Praag, M. and Cools, K. (2005) "The effects of performance measurement and compensation on motivation: an empirical study", *De Economist*, 153(3), pp. 303-29

¹¹ Cardy, L. and Leonard, B. (2011) *Performance Management: Concepts, Skills, and Exercises*. Delhi: M.E Sharpe.

¹² Kumar, J. (2012) "Performance appraisal and promotion process: A measure approach", *International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology*, 1(1), pp.1-6.

¹³ Maana, R. (2008), "Strategic Aspects of the Importance of Employee Management", *Journal of Diversity Management*, 3(1), pp.1-6.

5. Performance Appraisal and Employee Rewards

In an organizational environment, motivation is critical, as discussed in the preceding section. Its importance is primarily due to its ability to initiate, guide, channel, and maintain human behavior. Peters (2012)¹⁴ proposed Employees can be motivated by incentives like promotions and raises in wages in this context by using performance assessments. According to Herzberg's theory, extrinsic rewards can be used as incentives to increase performance. (Bassett 2005)¹⁵. Employees assessing timeliness, correctness, goal setting methods, and feedback channels are all part of performance appraisal satisfaction. (Dobbins1990)¹⁶. Longenekar, summarized

the fundamental worry of using a Performance Assessment as "the major concern is how best to utilize the appraisal process to inspire and reward subordinates". It is considered that the PA process consists of a succession of behaviours in which the appraiser observes, saves, and remembers and integrates appraise behaviour as needed. Wexley and Klimoxi (1984)¹⁷

6. Bonus Payments and Salary Increases

Pay-for-performance is widely held to be the most successful strategy for motivating employees, according to performance management literature. In this case, money serves as an extrinsic motivator by indirectly satisfying the

¹⁴ Petersen, J., Kaplan, E. and Samuels, A. (2007) "Effects of Subordinate Likeability and Balanced Scorecard Format on Performance-Related Judgments", *Advances in Accounting*, 23, pp.85-111.

¹⁵ Bassett-Jones, N. and Lloyd, C. (2005) "Does Herzberg's motivation theory have staying power?" *Journal of Management Development*, 24(10), pp.929 – 943.

¹⁶ Dobbins, G. H., Cardy, R. L., & Platz-Vieno, S. J. (1990). "A contingency approach to appraisal

satisfaction: an initial investigation of the joint effects of organisational variables and appraisal characteristics". *Journal of Management*, 16 (3), 619-632

¹⁷ Wexley K.N. & Klimoski R. (1984).

Performance Appraisal: An update.Pp 35 -79 in G R Ferris & K.R. Rowland (eds). *Research in Personnel and Human Resource Management*, Vol 2. Greenwich, C T: Jai Press

employee's needs through incentives and pay.¹⁸ Jensen and Murphy (2004) used the Pay-for-performance theory uses reinforcement theory to describe how remuneration is linked to performance by establishing specific goals. After these targets have been established, employees are paid accordingly. A desire to earn more money extrinsically pushes individuals to put out more effort and perform better in this situation.¹⁹ The proportion of a bonus or raise in salary is based on the results of performance reviews. Bonuses are given to employees who meet or exceed the set requirements, such as an additional 2% for exceeding sales targets. The whole procedure is simplified thanks to performance assessments.

7. Recognizing and Evaluating the Performance of Employees

An employee's motivation may be boosted by providing a platform for the recognition of successes through performance evaluations.²⁰ Recognizing an employee's good work involves giving them non-monetary personal awards that reinforce their good work habits. Commendations, incentives, and ceremonies, such as public celebrations and speeches, make up the bulk of this process.²¹ Managers and other higher-ups should show appreciation for their employees' achievements, according to previous study, because doing so can inspire creativity and the adoption of strategies that boost performance.²² Furthermore, Recognition has been found to stimulate workers to apply inventive problem-solving talents.²³

¹⁸ Anthony, R. and Govindarajan, V. (2007) *Management Control Systems*, 12th ed., Irwin, Singapore

¹⁹ Peterson, T.M. (2007) 'Motivation: How to increase project team performance', *Project Management Journal*, 38(4), pp. 60-69.

²⁰ Brun, J.-P. and Dugas, N. (2008) 'An analysis of employee recognition: perspectives on human resources practices', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19(4), pp. 716-730

²¹ Long, R.J. and Shields, J.L. (2010) 'From pay to praise? Non-cash employee recognition in Canadian and Australian firms', *The International Journal of*

Human Resource Management, 21(8), pp. 1145-1172

²² Nijhof, A., Krabbendam, K. and Looise, J.K. (2002) 'Innovation through exemptions: building upon the existing creativity of employees', *Technovation*, 22(11), pp. 675-83

²³ David, P., Song, M., Hayes, A. and Fredin, S. (2007) 'A cyclic model of information seeking in hyperlinked environments: The role of goals, self-efficacy, and intrinsic motivation', *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 65(2), Pages 170-182

8. Need for the study

With this research, employees are given feedback on their performance, which serves as both a mirror for their personal and professional growth and as an effective tool for management to take action in the face of obstacles that might jeopardize an employee's well-being. An evaluation system's importance may be determined by this study. A person's work analysis and the provision of superior support, help, and counselling strengthens both their job performance and their personal characteristics in the company when they make decisions about things like remuneration, training, and promotion and demotion. This study contributes to the advancement of organizational goals, allowing superiors to make better decisions on how to extract labour from subordinates. Providing information on performance rankings/helping to counsel/facilitating equitable compensation is one way to promote organizational effectiveness via the correction of employees for standard and enhanced performance and the suggestion of adjustments in employee behavior.

9. Research Objectives

10. The main aim of the study are

1. To analyze the Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee Motivation
2. To identify the challenges in appraising employees performance

11. Methodology

The study significantly used primary data. Some sources for secondary data were also browsed in order to deeply understand the phenomenon of performance appraisal as a basis for Job Satisfaction and Motivation to work. The primary data was collected as responses from a judgment sample of 200 respondents working in various IT industries using simple random sampling technique. The rationale for choosing the respondents was a minimum of a two year work experience in the same organization and being subjected to an annual Performance Appraisal

Findings

11.1. Demographic nature of the respondents

The nature of the sample respondents selected for the study has been summarized below in Table 1. The age, gender and experience of the respondents are considered in the study.

Table 1: Nature of the respondents

Nature	Category	N	%
Age	Below 25 years	42	21
	25-35 years	48	24
	36 – 45 years	54	27
	More than 45 years	56	28
Gender	Male	126	63
	Female	74	37
Experience	Up to 5 years	54	27
	6- 10 years	68	34
	More than 10 years	78	39
Total		200	100

The above table shows that 56 (28%) respondents are aged more than 45 years, 54 (27%) respondents aged between 36 and 45. 126 (63%) respondents are male and 74 (37%) respondents are female. 78 (39%) respondents have more than 10 years of experience and 68 (34%) are moderately experienced (between 6 and 10 years).

The performance appraisal system has significance effect in the human resource management. The identification of talented employees and retain them with the organization for better productivity and overall performance of human resource. It is an attempt to find the effect of the performance appraisal system on the employee's motivation.

11.2. The effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee Motivation

Table 2: Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee Motivation

Effect of performance appraisal	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank
Ratings are above average for performance.	2.97	1.232	5.80
It allows me to set my performance goals for each of the rating periods.	3.06	1.195	5.97
The aim of the performance evaluation procedure is well recognized.	2.98	1.127	5.54
Its approach fosters cooperation by rating performance depending on how they accomplish it.	3.13	1.140	6.11
Set the parameters for the work.	3.13	1.256	6.08
It finds inefficiencies in the work process and seeks to remedy them.	3.08	1.081	5.72
Ratings based on a wide range of recent actions. Work for which I am accountable is something for which I take ownership.	3.09	1.106	5.93
It aids in enhancing one's capacity to accomplish their work duties.	3.27	1.278	6.51

Performance of employees may be easily measured.	3.11	1.339	6.06
Ratings are above average for performance.	3.16	1.209	6.19
It allows me to set my performance goals for each of the rating periods.	3.21	1.140	6.10

The Table 2 indicates that the respondents feel that the performance appraisal system identifies the problems and helps to improve the productivity of each employee (6.51). Its role to improve the job performance of the employees is also identified as major factor (6.19). Third rank is given to the statement showing the appraisal system (6.11). The respondents also feel that the appraisal system helps to easily measure the performance of the employees (6.10). Other effects are followed after these effects on the employee's motivation.

11.3. The challenges in appraising employees performance

It is not easy adopt the performance appraisal system in an organization where the talented and skillful employees are working like a IT sector. This study is also attempt to understand the employees' opinion on the challenges in implementing the performance appraisal system. They are analyzed as below.

Table 3: Challenges in appraisal system

Challenges	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank
Manager gives fair feedback	3.28	0.796	6.90
The career recognizes me when I do a good job	3.05	1.099	6.18
My evaluator plays a significant role in my motivation	2.84	1.390	5.63
The ratings adequately reflects the performance	3.17	1.195	6.57
It reflects objectively of performance	3.19	1.056	6.60
Ratings is based on reasonable expectations from work	3.29	1.147	6.77
The manager is highly capable to rate performance	3.50	1.326	7.22
The relationship with manager	3.45	1.162	7.39
It does not manage me better	3.30	1.103	7.00
My evaluator is based about my job performance	2.92	1.173	5.65
The managers have reasonable expectations	2.97	1.431	6.02
Challenging to receive feedback	3.04	1.158	6.08

According to the mean ranks shown in the each challenges, it is found that the relationship between the manager or supervisor and the employees plays important role in the performance appraisal system (7.39). Secondly, the capability of the manager to rate the performance is also a huge challenge (7.22). Another big challenge has been identified as the performance appraisal system does not help

the employees to manage better (7.00). Forth one is, fair feedback given by managers is considered a big challenge (6.90). According to the result of the challenges, it is found that the role of the managers or superiors play main role in performance appraisal. Other challenges are ranked lesser than these factors.

12. Conclusion

In a short time, the company's rules are well-known to its employees, and the company's good name is established in the minds of its workers. It is recommended that the corporation use innovative techniques to provide high-quality services quickly and efficiently during employee measurements, with a particular emphasis on executive employee performance and their opinion. Management should concentrate on "best" HRM practices and design "studied" Performance assessment policies for workers as a new emphasis if the Organization achieves greater performance levels. The performance appraisal approach prevalent in the organization is fair. They are pleased with the current performance evaluation method, which is based on a conventional approach. Organizations now have the opportunity to use more current methods of assessment that are more successful.

13. Reference

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